

ENHANCING THE TESTING OF CERN'S LINUX SOFTWARE BUILDING SERVICE AND IMPROVING MONITORING

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

Linux Software Building Service – Koji, Linux Operating System, GitLab CI-CD Pipelines, Grafana, OpenSearch, Monitoring.

ABSTRACT

Selected to work as OpenLab Summer Student at CERN in the “Enhancing the Testing of CERN’s Linux Software Building Service And Improving Monitoring” project.

This report contains the work done over two months on two independent projects. In the first project, a Koji tag structure was created for the missing operating systems supported at CERN by the Linux team in the kojitest environment. Improvements to the Koji-tester pipeline were made to ensure that the most common Koji operations run successfully. It is quite an important task to maintain the quality of the Linux software building service, ensuring that upgrades with each new Koji release are smooth and reliable.

After the creation of a new OpenSearch indexes, the dashboards developed in Opensearch needed to be rebuilt. The Linux team decided to move it to Grafana, a very reliable monitor tool. There are twenty-seven Opensearch dashboards that need to be reviewed and moved to Grafana. We migrated 2 out of 27 to monitor Nomad jobs and <https://linuxsoft.cern.ch/> accesses.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	05
------------------------	-----------

2. PROJECT OVERVIEW	06
----------------------------	-----------

2.1 Enhancing the Testing of CERN's Linux Building Service

2.2 Migration of Dashboards from OpenSearch to Grafana

CONCLUSION	15
-------------------	-----------

FUTURE WORKS	15
---------------------	-----------

REFERENCES	16
-------------------	-----------

1. INTRODUCTION

Koji is a system that helps us to build and tracking the RPMs and images. It also facilitates the organization of packages through tags, which are essentially the names given to the package repositories.

CERN's Linux software building service uses Koji, which requires secure and reliable upgrades to ensure smooth functionality of the service. In order to effectively test and develop the Koji system, the CERN Linux team developed a GitLab project called Koji-Tester. The aim of the first project was to improve the pipeline of the Koji-Tester project by defining Koji tag structures for different operating systems supported at CERN, in the Kojitest environment.

In addition, monitoring is a very important task nowadays, and the Linux team uses OpenSearch to keep the logs of Nomad jobs and access to linuxsoft.cern.ch. Due to changes in the OpenSearch indexes, all the visualizations had to be reviewed and migrated to Grafana, a more flexible monitoring tool.

2. PROJECT OVERVIEW

a. Enhancing the Testing of CERN's Linux Building Service

2.a.1 Overview of Koji and Koji-Tester

Koji is a system that builds and tracks RPMs and images securely, [1]. Like any software, Koji may need to be upgraded. Koji-Tester is a pipeline with different tests that helps us ensure that koji.cern.ch (production) and kojitest.cern.ch (testing) are working fine, especially during upgrades, [2]. We always upgrade the kojitest environment and keep it for at least one week before we upgrade the koji production environment. I got Admin privileges to access the Kojitest environment in this project.

2.a.2 Objectives and Goals

The main goal of this project is to ensure that the Koji system works safely and smoothly for building RPMs, cloud images, and Docker images for different operating systems supported at CERN during any upgrade. **Table 1** shows the operating systems supported by the CERN Linux team and their deprecation dates.

Operating System	Deprecation Date	Supported by the Linux team
SLC 6: Scientific Linux CERN 6	30.11.2020	no
CC7: CERN CentOS 7	30.06.2024	no
CS8: CentOS Stream 8	30.09.2023	no
CS9: CentOS Stream 9	30.06.2023	no
RHEL7: Red Hat Enterprise Linux 7	30.06.2024	no
RHEL8: Red Hat Enterprise Linux 8	-	yes
RHEL9: Red Hat Enterprise Linux 9	-	yes
ALMA8: AlmaLinux 8	-	yes
ALMA9: AlmaLinux 9	-	yes

Table 1. Supported Operating Systems

The objective is that the Koji-Tester pipeline run each test successfully for all operating systems supported at CERN. Additionally, a pipeline schedule should be created to trigger the Koji-Tester pipeline daily on GitLab.

The tests included:

- RPM building
- Cloud images building
- CS8 Docker image building
- Alma 8 Docker image building
- Alma 9 Docker image building
- Driver Update Disks building

Figure 1 shows the failed tests when we triggered the Koji-Tester pipeline at the beginning of the project.

Figure 1. Triggered Pipeline at The Beginning

To achieve this goal, new Koji tags for supported OS should be created in the Kojitest environment. A tag is the repository name that will contain the packages associated with it.

2.a.3 Creating New Koji Tag structure

The Koji commands can be run on Lxplus or Aiadm. During the project, we connected Lxplus via SSH, as shown in **Figure 2**.

```
C:\Users\oztur>ssh zozturk@lxplus.cern.ch
The authenticity of host 'lxplus.cern.ch (2001:1458:201:e4::100:63d)' can't be established.
ED25519 key fingerprint is SHA256:x0tCWmpDSZenkpkC7zNvTW0l8eh3kXaStmqZC3UVcAk.
This host key is known by the following other names/addresses:
  C:\Users\oztur/.ssh/known_hosts:1: lxplus-gpu.cern.ch
Are you sure you want to continue connecting (yes/no/[fingerprint])? yes
Warning: Permanently added 'lxplus.cern.ch' (ED25519) to the list of known hosts.
(zozturk@lxplus.cern.ch) Password:
*****
```

Figure 2. Lxplus connection via SSH

Then, the tag structure should be created in the Kojitest environment. There is a profile argument to switch between Koji and Kojitest environments as shown in the **Figure 3**. First, we need to define the Kojitest profile, then we can run the Koji commands to create tags. The tag structure can change depending on the operating system.

```
Last login: Fri Aug 16 10:18:56 2024 from 2001:1458:204:1::101:4391
[zozturk@lxplus958 ~]$ KOJI_PROFILE=kojitest
[zozturk@lxplus958 ~]$ koji -p KOJI_PROFILE add-tag --arches "x86_64 aarch64" $TAG
```

Figure 3. Koji Profile

To achieve the goal of this project, we needed to define the Koji tag structure. There was already a tag structure defined for AlmaLinux 9. We started by defining the tag structure for AlmaLinux 8 because it is similar.

The screenshot shows the 'Buildsystem' web interface. The main content area displays 'Information for tag mytag9al-build' with the following details:

- Name: mytag9al-build
- ID: 1981
- Arches: x86_64 aarch64
- Locked: no
- Permission: none
- Maven Support?: no
- Include All Maven Builds?: no
- Inheritance: mytag9al-build
 - alma9-cern
 - cern9al-stable
 - builddsys9al-stable
 - alma9-defaults
 - mytag9al-testing

- External repos:
- alma9-baseos [bare] (inherited from alma9-defaults)
- alma9-appstream [bare] (inherited from alma9-defaults)
- alma9-crb [bare] (inherited from alma9-defaults)
- Repo created: Wed, 14 Aug 2024 08:29:41 CEST
- Packages: 33
- Packages (blocked packages included): 33
- Builds: 60
- Targets building from this tag: mytag9al
- Targets building to this tag: No build targets
- Extra options:
- mock.new_chroot: False

Figure 4. AlmaLinux 9 Tag

Figure 4 is an example of a AlmaLinux 9 tag, with the inheritance tag structure and the external repositories defined. These repositories can be defined in the Kojitests environment through Koji commands.

We need to check the local repositories names belonging to each distribution. These repositories are an upstream copy, and they can differ between OS. When we compare **Figure 5** and **Figure 6**, we can see that there is no CRB repository for AlmaLinux 8 like it is defined for AlmaLinux 9. The tagging processes should be made carefully, [3].

Name	Last modified	Size
Parent Directory	-	-
AppStream/	2024-08-07 08:01	-
BaseOS/	2024-08-07 08:00	-
CERN/	2024-08-07 08:02	-
COMPOSE_ID	2024-08-07 08:00	25
CRB/	2024-08-07 08:01	-
HighAvailability/	2024-08-07 08:01	-
NFV/	2024-08-07 08:02	-
RT/	2024-08-07 08:01	-
ResilientStorage/	2024-08-07 08:01	-
cloud/	2024-08-07 08:03	-
devel/	2024-08-07 08:02	-
extras/	2024-08-07 08:02	-
nfv/	2024-08-07 08:03	-
openafs/	2024-08-07 08:02	-
plus/	2024-08-07 08:02	-
snapshotdate.txt	2024-08-07 08:00	9
synergy/	2024-08-07 08:02	-
testing/	2024-08-07 08:02	-

Figure 5. AlmaLinux 9 CERN Local Repository

Figure 6. AlmaLinux 8 CERN Local Repository

Figure 7 shows the Koji commands to define the external repositories for AlmaLinux 9.

```

koji add-external-repo alma9-baseos 'https://linuxsoft.cern.ch/cern/alma/9/BaseOS/$arch/os/'
koji add-external-repo alma9-appstream 'https://linuxsoft.cern.ch/cern/alma/9/AppStream/$arch/os/'
koji add-external-repo alma9-crb 'http://linuxsoft.cern.ch/cern/alma/9/CRB/$arch/os/'

koji add-external-repo alma9-testing-baseos 'https://linuxsoft.cern.ch/cern/alma/9-testing/BaseOS/$arch/os/'
koji add-external-repo alma9-testing-appstream 'https://linuxsoft.cern.ch/cern/alma/9-testing/AppStream/$arch/os/'
koji add-external-repo alma9-testing-crb 'http://linuxsoft.cern.ch/cern/alma/9-testing/CRB/$arch/os/'

koji add-external-repo alma9-latest-baseos 'https://linuxsoft.cern.ch/cern/alma/.9-latest/BaseOS/$arch/os/'
koji add-external-repo alma9-latest-appstream 'https://linuxsoft.cern.ch/cern/alma/.9-latest/AppStream/$arch/os/'
koji add-external-repo alma9-latest-crb 'http://linuxsoft.cern.ch/cern/alma/.9-latest/CRB/$arch/os/'

```

Figure 7. External Repository Definition

Secondly, we need to create a base tag after defining external repositories, as shown in the Figure 8.

```

koji add-tag alma9-defaults --arches="x86_64 aarch64"

koji add-external-repo -t alma9-defaults alma9-baseos -p 30 --mode bare
koji add-external-repo -t alma9-defaults alma9-appstream -p 40 --mode bare
koji add-external-repo -t alma9-defaults alma9-crb -p 50 --mode bare

koji add-group alma9-defaults build
koji add-group alma9-defaults srpm-build
koji add-group-pkg alma9-defaults build bash bzip2 coreutils cpio diffutils findutils gawk gcc gcc-c++ grep gzip info kernel-rpm-macros krb5-lib
koji add-group-pkg alma9-defaults srpm-build bash bzip2 coreutils cpio diffutils findutils gawk gcc gcc-c++ grep gzip info kernel-rpm-macros krb

```

Figure 8. Creating Base Tag

Other tags need to be created in a similar way. It is important to check the paths and repositories carefully for each OS, as there can be differences in the tag creation process.

At the end of the project, each operating system supported at CERN should have a similarly defined tag structure. After completing the process, we need to trigger the Koji-tester pipeline to test the koji commands. **Figure 9** shows that after triggering the pipeline, the pipeline successfully passed each test as a result of the changes made.

Figure 9. Triggered Pipeline at The End

2.a.4 Scheduling Pipeline

Figure 10. Scheduling Pipeline on GitLab

It is important to check if some of the test are failing or not on daily basis. It allows us to act promptly. Automating this process was important for the Linux team. We need to schedule the Koji-Tester pipeline to run daily on GitLab, as shown in **Figure 10**.

An alert integrated with the Mattermost Linux alert channel was created for this pipeline schedule. This alert notifies the Linux team about successful or failed pipeline runs. An example of alert message is shown in **Figure 11**.

Figure 11. Created Alert in Mattermost

b. Migration of Dashboards from OpenSearch to Grafana

Dashboards allows us to query, transform, visualize, and understand your data, no matter where it's stored. To track access to linuxsoft.cern.ch and Nomad logs, the Linux team created dashboards on OpenSearch, [4]. OpenSearch indexes changed because the Linux team started to use monit-logs. However, it is not possible to change the index on OpenSearch visualizations. It means that the dashboards need to be recreated again with the new index. This is not flexible in the long term. Therefore, the 27 dashboards in OpenSearch need to be reviewed and migrated to Grafana, which is a more adaptable monitoring tool. My goal on this project was to migrate some of these dashboards. **Figure 12** shows the damaged Opensearch dashboards due to index changes.

Figure 12. OpenSearch Dashboard

2.b.1 Creating Dashboards on Grafana

Within the scope of this project, we had to create different chart types and explore the Grafana tool, [5]. One of the dashboards needed to be migrated was table showing the nomad logs. We created filters by tag, message and task to filter the Nomad logs on Grafana. These filters can be created by defining variables in Grafana. An example of a variable definition is shown in **Figure 13**.

Figure 13. Variable Definition on Grafana

Using these defined variables and Lucene queries on Grafana, we can filter the logs and create new charts. For instance, **Figure 14** shows a Lucene query that filters the logs according to the tag and task name.

Figure 14. Example Lucene Query on Grafana

On Grafana is also possible to use transformations to manipulate the dashboards, for instance: organizing fields, extracting fields, reducing rows, etc. During this migration process, we used the Grafana documentation. Out of the 27 OpenSearch dashboards, we have successfully migrated 2 so far.

3. CONCLUSION

These projects are significant achievements for the Linux team in the long term. By the conclusion of the project focused on enhancing the testing of CERN's Linux software building service, we had a successful testing setup to ensure smooth and reliable upgrades of the Koji system. We also strated a big project were we need to migrate and review 27 dashboards from OpenSearch to Grafana.

During my time at CERN, we had the opportunity to work with tools like, GitLab, Bash, Opendsearch and Grafana.

4. FUTURE WORKS

In future work, a new tag structure needs to be defined for the new OS, for instance AlmaLinux10 and RHEL10 on Koji and Kojitest environment. There are still 25 dashboards that need to be reviewed and migrated to Grafana.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Koji Documentation
<https://docs.pagure.org/koji/HOWTO/>

- [2] Koji-Tester Project Repository
<https://gitlab.cern.ch/linuxsupport/testing/koji-tester>

- [3] Repository of Alma 8
<https://linuxsoft.cern.ch/cern/alma/8/>

- [4] OpenSearch Dashboards
<https://opensearch.org/docs/latest/about/>

- [5] Grafana Documentation
<https://grafana.com/docs/grafana/latest/>